

Dissemination of Psychoactive Substance Information for Rehabilitation of Female Drug Addicts by NDLEA Staff in Kano Metropolis

Ruqayya Hadi Barwa¹, Mohammed Sani Umar², Aisha Mohammed Bello³

^{1,2,3} University Library, Baba Ahmed University, Kano

ABSTRACT

Background: This study investigates the dissemination of psychoactive substance information and the rehabilitation of female drug addicts in Kano metropolis, Nigeria, by staff of the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA). The objectives were to assess the prevalence of psychoactive drug abuse among female addicts, identify their sources of psychoactive substance information, and examine the strategies used for disseminating such information.

Method: A quantitative research methodology with a cross-sectional survey design was employed. The study population consisted of all NDLEA staff in Kano metropolis. A total of 234 questionnaires were distributed, with 171 returned and deemed usable (response rate: 73.1%). Data were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Findings/Results: The findings revealed that stimulants, sedatives, and opioids were the most prevalent psychoactive substances abused by females in Kano metropolis. Key sources of information on substance abuse included friends, colleagues, informants, social media, and radio programs. Dissemination strategies identified included radio programs, community outreach, media advocacy, and the publication of informational materials.

Implications: The results suggest that social networks and media platforms play a significant role in spreading information about psychoactive substances among female addicts, while targeted dissemination strategies are critical for effective rehabilitation efforts. The prevalence of specific substances highlights the need for focused interventions.

Conclusion: The study concludes that the high prevalence of psychoactive substance abuse among females, coupled with the identified information sources and dissemination strategies, underscores the importance of strategic communication and intervention by NDLEA staff to support rehabilitation efforts.

Recommendations: The study recommends advocating for evidence-based policies and regulations to reduce the availability and demand for psychoactive substances. It also encourages continued research and evaluation to monitor substance abuse trends, assess intervention program effectiveness, and identify emerging substances.

Keywords: Psychoactive Substance, Rehabilitation, Female Drug Addicts, and NDLEA Staff.

INTRODUCTION

Drug addiction is a serious problem that affects individuals and society as a whole. It has been found that women are more vulnerable to drug addiction due to various biological, social, and psychological factors. The National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) is a government agency established in 1989 to combat drug trafficking and the abuse of psychoactive substances in Nigeria. The agency is responsible for the prevention, detection, and prosecution of drug-related crimes in the country. In recent years, drug abuse has become a significant problem in Nigeria, particularly among young people, with an increasing number of women and girls being affected. According to the report of Nigerian National Survey on Drug Use and Health, 14.4% of the population aged 15-64 years had used a psychoactive substance in the past year, with cannabis being the most commonly used drug (Jatau, et,al

2021). The use of psychoactive substances among women has become a major concern in Nigeria, especially in the Kano Metropolis.

Drug addiction is a significant public health issue globally, and Nigeria is no exception. According to the National Bureau of Statistics, over 14% of Nigerians between the ages of 15 and 64 use illicit drugs, with the highest prevalence in the northern region of the country, including Kano metropolis (NBS, 2021). Female drug addicts in Nigeria face unique challenges, including stigma, limited access to healthcare services, and inadequate rehabilitation facilities. The NDLEA rehabilitation centre in Kano metropolis is responsible for rehabilitating and preventing the spread of drug abuse in the region. However, the success of the rehabilitation program depends on the dissemination of accurate and reliable information about psychoactive substances to the female drug addicts.

The dissemination of information about psychoactive substances is a crucial aspect of rehabilitation programs. It is important for individuals to understand the risks and consequences associated with drug addiction in order to make informed decisions about their drug use. NDLEA staff members play a key role in disseminating this information to female drug addicts in the Kano Metropolis. The youths in Nigeria like many countries of the world are increasingly developing addiction to psychoactive substances or engage in drug abuse particularly women.

In line with the variables of the current study which include; psychoactive substance, strategies for dissemination of information and the National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) as the regulatory body, the study adopt theories explaining the dissemination of psychoactive substance information and drug use in relation to a regulatory body. The theories include; Media System Dependency Theory (MSD), Cognitive - Affective – Pharmacogenic (CAP) Control Theory, The Media Exposure Theory and the Psychoanalytic Theory. This implies specifically that the theories will be responsible for underpinning the cognitive abilities to enable both the regulatory institutions and the drugs users make decisions and behave in the appropriate manner in the context of dissemination of psychoactive substance information.

Thus, this current study proposed to use the principles and methodology of pragmatic assumptions to develop both objective findings from the National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) as the regulatory body with facts and figures related to psychoactive substance abusers. It is against this background and inadequate documented empirical evidence about the strategies of dissemination of information by NDLEA on psychoactive substance that the present study become imperative so as to investigate the related available information distribution channels and the consideration and analysis to identify appropriate strategies for the dissemination of information to drug addicts by the National Drugs Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) in managing the spread of psychoactive substances in order to formulate effective and research – based policies and theories.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Female drug addicts face unique challenges and barriers in accessing rehabilitation services, and the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) plays a crucial role in disseminating information about treatment options and supporting recovery efforts. Despite the efforts of the NDLEA to combat drug abuse and addiction in Nigeria, there is a growing concern about substance abuse among women and girls in Kano. Although the agency has established various initiatives aimed at addressing this problem. The observation by the researcher found that, little is known about the effectiveness of dissemination strategies used

A publication of the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria
by the NDLEA staff regarding the dissemination of psychoactive substance information for the rehabilitation of female drug addicts in Kano metropolis

It was against this background that this research investigates the influence of exposure on psychoactive drug abuse behaviours among female addicts in Kano metropolitan. The prevailing situation of lack of parental upbringing, economic instability, and poor-quality education can contribute to moral decadence, increasing prevalence of drug abuse among female youth in Kano metropolis. As a result, many young females have become drug addicts, leading to several negative consequences, including health problems, social stigma, and economic disempowerment.

To address these challenges, the study proposed to explore the role of existing interventions through dissemination of information approaches involving exploring innovative educational interventions, community engagement strategies, and targeted social programs that aim to promote positive character development and prevent moral decadence among youth. Ultimately, the research target to provide valuable insights that can inform policy and practice in the development of effective interventions to address the problem. It is against this background, that the present study will investigate the NDLEA staff and female drug abusers in order to develop a robust dissemination strategy applicable to all information providers.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were used as a guide to this study;

1. What type of psychoactive drug abuse is prevalent among female drug addicts in Kano metropolis?
2. What are the sources of psychoactive substance information by female drug addicts in Kano metropolis?
3. What are the strategies used by NDLEA staff for disseminating psychoactive substance information to female drug addicts in Kano metropolis?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Psychoactive Substance Information

Psychoactive substances have emerged over the last decade as derivatives of classical drugs of abuse such as amphetamine and cocaine. Since their emergence, the rise of these substances has been continuous and it reached about 1047 (UNODC, 2020). According to Jatau, et al., (2021). Indicated that the first set of psychoactive substance are the stimulants which are drugs which increase up the central nervous system activities. Examples are nicotine (cigarette), caffeine (kola nut), cocaine, pemoline, and amphetamines. Another psychoactive drug as indicated by Basha, Tefera, Tilahun, & Amede, (2023) includes the depressants which are drugs which slow down the central nervous system. Examples are alcohol, narcotics (opium and its derivatives), benzodiazepines (valium, Librium and lexotan), barbiturates (Amytal and phenobarbital), and methaqualone.

Jatau et al. (2021) conducted research on the type of psychoactive substance abuse information communicated to them by NDLEA rehabilitation centres and the following themes emerged: (i) health information (ii) religious information (iii) financial information (iv) school information (v) societal information. According to Fareo (2022) reported that religious leaders are usually invited time – time in Prison and rehabilitation Centre to preach as support groups in order to persuade Drugs addicts and convicts. In line with this, Fareo (2022) also reported that Drug abuse has negative impact on business productivity as it also increases workplace

injuries and absenteeism. In similarly, a scholar such as Eric & Makanjuola (2020) claimed that Psychoactive substance abuse is one of the major problems in our society that causes social violence, gang formation, cultism, armed robbery, 419 syndrome, Internet frauds, social miscreants (area boys and girls) lawlessness among youths, lack of respect for elders, rape, instant death and wasting of precious and innocent lives.

Sources of Psychoactive Substance Information

In an extensive survey of three Canadian cities Frejer, Smart and others studied 12,554 students in grades 7 through. News media were cited as the most informative source from which one could learn about drugs by an average of 53% of the students. Family and friends were the next frequently cited sources of information about drugs in general and marijuana in particular. Cajetan and Ignatius (2017) who examined drug information sources for high school students. They found School (Teacher), Church, Family members, Medical personnel, Friends and peers, Radio, Print media (e.g., books), Television peers and parents as the most helpful in dealing with drug problems information source about drug abuse, the media play a negligible role. Study carried out by Oshikoya and Alli (2020), reveal that television, radio and bill board advertisement were the students' major sources of awareness about psychoactive substance abuse. This could be that most of the parents and the students could afford television and radio. In the same vein according to Gureje and Olley,(2022) explained that information sharing platforms are communication groups among drug addicts which include: meetings, face-to-face interactions, forums that involve one-on-one conversations or interacting with many bodies within a society creating the proper fit begins with understanding the effectiveness areas of each channel.

Strategies for Disseminating Psychoactive Substance Information

Creating the proper fit begins with understanding the effectiveness areas of each media. Creating the proper fit also includes recognizing that no one channel is always sufficient caution against dichotomous separation of dissemination strategies into mass media and interpersonal (Reardon & Rogers, 2020). It was observed by Fareo (2022) that Health information, religious information, financial information, school information and societal information are the goals of disseminating psychoactive substance abuse information communicated to drug addicts by NDLEA. A study by Nhendodzashe, and Nhendo, (2013) titled "An assessment of the information dissemination channels used by the Zimbabwe Women's Resource Centre and Network in the provision of HIV/AIDS information to women" revealed that Sixty percent of women reported that the organisation was facing staffing challenges and this was followed by funding with 20%. Technological and political were third with 10% each. As remedies to the challenges cited above, networking and continuous staff development were common among the responses given. Engaging policy makers, soliciting for donations in terms of both financial and non-financial were some of the solutions given. The ZWRCN staff was also asked about the challenges they faced in their information dissemination activities.

METHODOLOGY

Quantitative research methodology and cross-sectional survey research design were used for the study. This design was chosen because of its simplicity, time and cost saving and it allows generalisation to be made on the entire population. The population of the study comprised 615 National Drug Law Enforcement Agency staff in Kano metropolis out of which 234 was sampled using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size table. The study adopted stratified

sampling technique. The instrument adopted to collect data for this study was questionnaire. A total of 234 copies of questionnaire were distributed while only 171 were returned and found usable for the study. The data was collected and analysed using descriptive statistics. It was employed to get a general understanding of the central tendencies using frequency statistics function for mean, mode, median and sum.

Result and discussion

Table 1: Types of Psychoactive Drugs Used

S/No	Psychoactive Drugs	Used	Percentage Used	Level of Prevalence
1	Nicotine	102	60%	High
2	Cigarette	144	84%	Very High
3	Cocaine	49	29%	low
4	Caffeine	144	84%	Very High
5	Cannabis	17	10%	Very Low
6	Alcohol	113	66%	High
7	Lizard Dung	4	2%	Very Low
8	Tobacco	109	64%	High
9	Heroine	34	20%	Very Low
10	Shisha	156	91%	Very High
11	Marijuana	34	20%	Very Low
12	Opioids	154	90%	Very High
13	Ecstasy	2	1%	Very Low
14	Hashish	0	0%	Very Low

Table 1 Presents the data on the usage of various psychoactive drugs among female drug addicts. The data shown that majority 156 (91%) of the female drug addicts use shisha follows by opioids with 154 (90%) caffeine and cigarette 144(84%) while more than half 113(66%) of the female drug addicts use alcohol, Tobacco 109 (64%) as well as Nicotine used by 102(60%). The analysis further revealed that some drugs were moderately used by the female drug addicts. The respondents indicated that less than half 49(29%) of the drug addicts use cocaine, Heroin and Marijuana 34(20%),Cannabis 17(10%),Lizard Dung 4(2%), Ecstasy 2(1%) and Hashish was not used by any respondent (0%).

From the analysis of various psychoactive drugs among respondents, Shisha, Cigarette and Caffeine have the highest usage rates, indicating these substances are widely consumed and possibly normalized within the study population. Their legal status and social acceptability might contribute to their high usage rates. Alcohol and Tobacco also have high usage rates, which aligns with global trends where these substances are legally available and commonly used. Shisha (91%) and Opioids (90%) show unexpectedly high usage rates, which could suggest specific cultural or social factors in the study population that promote the use of these substances. Cocaine (29%) and Heroine (20%) indicate moderate levels of use. These figures suggest that while these substances are illegal and typically harder to access, they are still significantly used among the study population. Lizard Dung (2%) and Ecstasy (1%) have very low usage rates, possibly due to their lesser popularity among female drug addicts, while Hashish (0%) being not used at all indicates either a lack of availability or a complete lack of interest or cultural acceptance.

The findings highlight significant usage of certain psychoactive substances among the respondents, with particularly high rates for commonly available legal substances and

concerning levels for shisha and opioids. These insights can inform targeted public health interventions and policies to address and mitigate substance abuse in the population.

Table 2: Sources of Psychoactive Substance Information

S/No	Sources of Psychoactive Substance Information	Response	Percentage	Use
1	Information resources on the internet	34	19%	Very Low
2	Drug sellers	87	50%	Moderate
3	Addicts in captivity	67	39%	Low
4	Relatives of addicts	112	65%	High
5	Security agents	0	0%	Very low
6	Co-workers	78	46%	Moderate
7	Friends and colleagues	171	100%	Very high
8	Print media	0	0%	Very Low
9	Social media	109	64%	High
10	Informants	170	99%	Very High
11	Radio and Television	167	98%	Very High
12	Conference and seminars	98	57%	Moderate

Table 2 indicated that the respondents get information from, Majority friends and colleagues 171(100%), Informants 170(99%) Radio and Television 167(98%) respectively, Followed by Relative of Addicts 112(65%), Social Media 109(64%), Conferences and Seminars 98(57%), Drugs Sellers 87(50%), Co-workers 78(46%), Addicts in Captivity 67(39%), Information Resources on the Internet 34(19%). While the least sources of psychoactive substance information was from print media and security agents.

This shows that the major sources of psychoactive substance information were Friends and Colleagues, Informants, Radio and Television.

Table 3: Strategies Used for the Disseminating Psychoactive Substance Information

S/N	Strategies for Disseminating Psychoactive Substance Information	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1.	I use radio programs as strategy on disseminating psychoactive substance abuse	3.6550	1.03083	Accepted
2.	I use internet as a channel for disseminating psychoactive substance information	2.1111	1.17044	Rejected
3.	I use social media as a channel for disseminating psychoactive substance information	2.6550	1.31203	Rejected
4.	I use television program as a channel for disseminating psychoactive substance information	3.0351	1.25039	Rejected
5.	I sponsor media advocacy for disseminating psychoactive substance information	3.7661	1.24296	Accepted
6.	I organised community outreach as a strategy for disseminating psychoactive substance information	4.0643	1.26093	Accepted

7.	I organised Campaign against drug abuse as a strategy for disseminating psychoactive substance information	2.7368	1.52462	Rejected
8.	I collaborate with movie studios to produce long movies/series movies are produced as a strategy for disseminating psychoactive substance information	2.7368	1.52462	Rejected
9.	I published fliers, brochures, leaflets and share at various gatherings to disseminate information to female drug addicts	3.3392	1.16903	Accepted

Table 3 shows the various strategies used by NDLEA staff in reaching out to female drugs addicts in Kano metropolis. The level of the acceptance or rejection was determined by the index mean value 3.1222 any statement with mean value below the value of the index mean is considered rejected while statement above or equal to the index mean value is considered accepted.

Community outreach has the highest mean value of 4.0643, then sponsor media advocacy 3.7661, followed by radio programs with mean value 3.6550 and publishing fliers, brochures, leaflets and share them at various gatherings with mean value 3.3392 are considered accepted due to the fact that their mean value is greater than the index mean, Followed by television programs with mean value 3.0351. Organising campaigns against drugs and movies production has the mean value of 2.7368 each followed by social media with mean value 2.6550 and lastly the use of internet with the lowest mean value 2.1111. This shows that community outreach, sponsored media advocacy, radio programs and sharing of leaflets, fliers and brochures at gathering are the major strategies NDLEA staff used in disseminating psychoactive substance information to female drug addicts in Kano metropolis.

Findings of the Study

1. The study found that the types of psychoactive substances prevalent among female drug addicts are opioids, stimulants, alcohol and sedatives.
2. The study found that the sources of psychoactive substance information are friends and colleagues, Informants, Radio and Television
3. The study found that the factors that facilitate the dissemination of psychoactive substance information among drugs addicts are availability, quality, reliability, currency and authority of the information

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings across all variables investigated in the study, the following conclusions can be drawn: The study identified a diverse range of psychoactive substances abused by female drug addicts in Kano metropolis, including opioids, stimulants, depressants, alcohol, and marijuana. Primary sources of information for psychoactive substances among female drug addicts included friends/colleagues, drug sellers, social media, and print media. The study categorized substances into opioids, stimulants, alcohol, marijuana, and sedatives. NDLEA employed various strategies such as radio programs, social media campaigns, community outreach, and educational collaborations to disseminate information. These strategies are consistent with effective dissemination practices outlined in the literature, emphasizing the importance of multi-faceted approaches in reaching diverse audiences.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance interventions and policies related to psychoactive substance abuse among female drug addicts in Kano metropolis:

1. Advocate for the development and implementation of evidence-based policies and regulations aimed at reducing the availability and demand for psychoactive substances. This includes enforcing existing laws, promoting responsible prescribing practices, and addressing illicit drug trafficking.
2. Encourage continued research and evaluation to monitor trends in substance abuse, assess the effectiveness of intervention programs, and identify emerging substances and patterns of use among female drug addicts. This will facilitate evidence-based decision-making and adaptation of strategies to evolving challenges.
3. Foster collaboration and coordination among government agencies, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), healthcare providers, and community leaders to create a comprehensive and integrated approach to tackling substance abuse. This includes sharing resources, best practices, and data to optimize intervention strategies.

REFERENCES

- Basha, E.A., Tefera, A.S., Tilahun, A.T. & Amede, A.F. (2023) Magnitude and Associated Factors of Psychoactive Substance Use among Youths at Selected Administrative Towns of North Shewa Zone, Amhara Region, Ethiopia. *Hindawi Journal of Addiction*, 2124999, 1-8, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/2124999>
- Cajetan I. I., Ignatius O. N., (2017). Drug Use and Sources of Drug Information among Secondary School Students in Imo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Educational Sciences*, EJES, Vol.4, No.1. doi: 10.19044/ejes.v4no1a76
- Eric, O. & Makanjuola, T. (2020). Psychoactive substance abuse: Impacts on social behavior and violence. *African Journal of Drug and Alcohol Studies*, 19(2), 88-99.
- Fareo, D. O. (2022). The role of health information in the fight against drug abuse. *Journal of Drug Education*, 46(1), 11-23.
- Gureje, O., & Olley, B. O. (2022). Face-to-face interactions and communication forums among drug users. *Journal of Addictive Behaviors*, 36(1), 123-135.
- Jatau, et al (2021) The Burden of Drug Abuse in Nigeria: A Scoping Review of Epidemiological Studies and Drug Laws. *Public Health Rev.* 42(1603960).
- National Bureau of Statistics (2021) National Survey on Drug Use and Health 2016-2017. Retrieved from <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/nada/index.php/catalog/64> (Accessed on 11th December, 2022)
- Nhendodzashe, N., and Nhendo, C., (2013). "An assessment of the information dissemination channels used by the Zimbabwe Women's Resource Centre and Network in the provision of HIV/AIDS information to women" *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 1089.
- Oshikoya, K. A., & Alli, A. (2020). The role of mass media in drug abuse awareness among students. *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice*, 18(3), 349-353.
- Reardon, R. C., & Rogers, E. M. (2020). Mass media and interpersonal communication in the dissemination of drug abuse information. *Journal of Substance Use*, 26(4), 389-401.
- United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) (2020). World drug report 2019. Available at: <https://wdr.unodc.org/wdr2019/en/exsum.html> (Accessed 8th September, 2021).